

A CAMERON AND ERDŐS CONJECTURE ON COUNTING PRIMITIVE SETS

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Abstract

Let $f(n)$ count the number of subsets of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ without an element dividing another. In this paper we show that $f(n)$ grows like the n -th power of some real number, in the sense that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n)^{1/n}$ exists. This confirms a conjecture of Cameron and Erdős, proposed in a paper where they studied a number of similar problems, including the well known “Cameron-Erdős Conjecture” on counting sum-free subsets.

1. The Result

Let $f(n)$ be the number of subsets of $[n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that no element divides another - call these sets *primitive*. One easily notices that $2^n \geq f(n) \geq 2^{n/2}$ (since subsets of the second half are all primitive), motivating Cameron and Erdős to question whether there is an exact real number characterizing the exponential growth of this function [1]. We confirm their conjecture.

Theorem. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n)^{1/n}$ exists.

Proof. We will study the auxiliary and more structured $f(n, k)$, which we define to be the number of subsets of $[n]$ such that no two elements have an integer ratio for which all prime factors are at most p_k (the k -th prime number). Call these sets k -core. The crux of the proof will be a little argument that shows that if, for each k , $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n, k)^{1/n}$ exists, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n)^{1/n}$ also exists. This is somewhat surprising, because if one doesn't think about this in the right way, it may seem that it is necessary to send k to infinity together with n , in order to obtain the desired limit. That said, we divide the proof into two parts:

Part 1: If we assume that, for each k , $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n, k)^{1/n} = \alpha_k$ exists, then the α_k decrease to some limit α and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n)^{1/n}$ exists and is equal to α .

Part 2: For each fixed k , $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n, k)^{1/n}$ in fact exists.

Proof of part 1. Let $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n, k)^{1/n} = \alpha_k$. Clearly $f(n, k+1) \leq f(n, k)$ (because the condition of being $k+1$ -core is more restrictive than the condition of being k -core). By taking $1/n$ powers and limits we get that α_k are a decreasing sequence. Since they are non-negative, it follows that the α_k must have a limit α .

Since $f(n) \leq f(n, k)$ for all k , we get $\limsup f(n)^{1/n} \leq \alpha_k$ for each k , which gives $\limsup f(n)^{1/n} \leq \alpha$.

Now we need an inequality for the other side. For that, we notice that for a k -core subset of $[n]$, if the elements less than $\frac{n}{k}$ are removed we get a primitive subset. That is because the ratio of any two remaining elements is less than k , so if one element divided another then their ratio would be an integer less than k . All prime factors of such an integer are less than p_k , which contradicts that the original set is k -core. Hence this operation maps k -core sets to primitive sets. Also, it is clear that this operation maps at most $2^{n/k}$ sets to the same set (because two sets mapped to the same set may disagree only on the first n/k elements). This gives the inequality

$$f(n, k) \leq 2^{n/k} f(n).$$

By taking $1/n$ power and taking n to infinity this gives

$$\liminf f(n)^{1/n} \geq \alpha_k 2^{-1/k},$$

for all k . By making $k \rightarrow \infty$ we get $\liminf f(n)^{1/n} \geq \alpha$. So

$$\alpha \leq \liminf f(n)^{1/n} \leq \limsup f(n)^{1/n} \leq \alpha,$$

which completes the proof that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n)^{1/n}$ exists and is equal to α .

Proof of part 2. Fix k . Let $S = \{p_1, \dots, p_k\}$ and let $D = p_1 \cdots p_k$ be the product of the first k primes. Each integer can be written uniquely as a product aR where a only has prime factors in S and $(R, D) = 1$. Integers with distinct values of R cannot have an integer ratio with prime factors in S . So we partition the integers in $[n]$ according to their value of R , and the total number of k -core subsets of $[n]$ is just the product of the number of k -core subsets of each part. We also notice that each part consists of the naturals of the form aR , where a runs over the naturals $1 \leq \frac{n}{R}$ with all prime factors in S . Hence, if we define $P_k(x)$ to be the number of k -core (or simply primitive) subsets of the set of naturals $\leq x$ with all prime factors in S , we get

$$f(n, k) = \prod_{1 \leq R \leq n, (R, D) = 1} P_k \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{R} \right\rfloor \right).$$

Now set $\epsilon > 0$ to be chosen later. We first want to show that the first ϵn terms of this product do not contribute substantially. For these terms we use the bound

$$P_k(x) \leq 2^{(1+\log x)^k}.$$

We obtain this by bounding $P_k(x)$ above by the number of subsets of the set of naturals $\leq x$ with all prime factors in S , and we bound the size of this set by $(1 + \log x)^k$ by noticing that each $p_1^{a_1} \cdots p_k^{a_k} \leq x$ is associated to a distinct k -tuple (a_1, \dots, a_k) with $a_i \leq \log x$. Hence,

$$\prod_{1 \leq R \leq \epsilon n, (R,D)=1} P_k\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{R} \right\rfloor\right) \leq \prod_{1 \leq R \leq \epsilon n} 2^{(1+\log \frac{n}{R})^k} \leq 2^{\epsilon n(1+\log n)^k}.$$

The product of the first ϵn terms is also ≥ 1 , so we get

$$f(n, k) = 2^{O(\epsilon n(1+\log n)^k)} \prod_{\epsilon n < R \leq n, (R,D)=1} P_k\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{R} \right\rfloor\right).$$

Now $\frac{n}{R}$ is always between 1 and $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$. For each integer l between 1 and $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$ there are $n(\frac{1}{l} - \frac{1}{l+1}) + O(1)$ integers R from ϵn to n with $\lfloor \frac{n}{R} \rfloor = l$. And this is a run of consecutive numbers, so $n(\frac{1}{l} - \frac{1}{l+1}) \frac{\phi(D)}{D} + O(D)$ of these numbers are prime with D (ϕ is the Euler totient function). Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} f(n, k)^{1/n} &= 2^{O(\epsilon(1+\log n)^k)} \prod_{1 \leq l \leq \frac{1}{\epsilon}} P_k(l)^{(\frac{1}{l} - \frac{1}{l+1}) \frac{\phi(D)}{D} + \frac{O(D)}{n}} \\ &= 2^{O(\epsilon(1+\log n)^k + \frac{D(1+\log 1/\epsilon)^k}{\epsilon n})} \prod_{1 \leq l \leq \frac{1}{\epsilon}} P_k(l)^{(\frac{1}{l} - \frac{1}{l+1}) \frac{\phi(D)}{D}}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we used the bound $P_k(l) \leq 2^{(1+\log l)^k} \leq 2^{(1+\log 1/\epsilon)^k}$ again. Finally, we choose $\epsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$. By making $n \rightarrow \infty$, the error terms go to zero, and the number of terms in the product goes to infinity, so in order to prove that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n, k)^{1/n}$ exists it is enough to show that

$$\prod_{l=1}^{\infty} P_k(l)^{(\frac{1}{l} - \frac{1}{l+1}) \frac{\phi(D)}{D}}$$

is a convergent product (and the limit will be equal to this product). Indeed, by the same bound for $P_k(x)$ as before, it is enough to prove that $\sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+\log l)^k}{l(l+1)}$ is convergent, which is true. Hence the proof is complete. \square

Unfortunately our attempts up to now have failed to find the value of α (in some reasonable sense). This solution essentially reduces the original limit to a “smoothed” version of itself, in terms of the P_k , which is guaranteed to converge - but because we don’t know much else about the P_k , attempts to find the limit end up being circular. It is also amusing to notice that if one looks only at the infinite

product formula we found for α_k , it is not obvious that these form a decreasing sequence. One needs the “combinatorial” argument from part 1 to establish that, and this seems to be a considerable barrier to making sense out of the limit of α_k through this formula.

Reference

- [1] Cameron, P.J; Erdős, P. On the number of sets of integers with various properties, *Number Theory (Banff, AB, 1988)*, 61-79, de Gruyter, Berlin, 1990.